

“Exposure Assessment in Inorganic Arsenic”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Inorganic arsenic (iAs) toxicity refers to the adverse health effects caused by exposure to inorganic arsenic compounds, which are highly toxic and can cause severe health issues. These effects can manifest both acutely and chronically, depending on the level and duration of exposure. Acute exposure to high levels of iAs can cause immediate health effects, which can be life-threatening if not addressed promptly. Chronic exposure to lower levels of iAs over an extended period can lead to a wide range of serious health issues.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.5.4. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary inorganic arsenic intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the benchmark dose lower confidence limit based on a benchmark response (BMR) of 5% (BMDL₀₅) of 0.06 µg iAs/kg bw per day on skin cancer used also in EFSA's last scientific opinion (2024), and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary inorganic arsenic exposure.

Mean and 95th percentile exposure estimates at the MB scenario were calculated as 0.113 and 0.308 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). The Reference Point (0.06 µg/kg bw per day) for skin cancer is below the average dietary exposure estimates for iAs for the whole population. Therefore, the MOEs range between 0.5 for mean consumers and 0.2 at the 95th percentile exposure, respectively. These MOEs are relatively low and raise a health concern for skin cancer.

It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. Infants, toddlers and other children had two- or three-times higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight. Similarly to EFSA's findings the Reference Point (0.06 µg/kg bw per day) for skin cancer was within the range of the dietary exposure estimates for iAs for all population classes (0.02–1.74 µg/kg bw per day).

Rice (11.9%) was the major contributor to the iAs intake, twice higher than the other food categories, cereal flakes (5.0%), poultry meat (4.5%), mineral water (4.3%), fish (3.4%) followed by other food categories. In all population classes, with the exception of infants and elderly, rice was the major contributor. For infants, infant formula and cereal-based baby food were the main contributors to the iAs exposure, while the consumption of fish in the elderly population contributed higher to iAs intake than rice.

2 Introduction

Inorganic arsenic (iAs) refers to compounds containing arsenic that are not bonded with carbon. These compounds are commonly found in the environment, particularly in minerals, ores, and groundwater. Unlike organic arsenic compounds, which are generally less toxic and found in seafood, inorganic arsenic compounds are highly toxic and can pose significant health risks. Inorganic Arsenic can also be produced by human activities such as the use of pesticides, herbicides, and fertilizers, mining, smelting, and the production of glass and semiconductors, and the use of chromated copper arsenate (CCA) in pressure-treated wood.

Inorganic Arsenic Exposure have several health effects. Acute exposure to iAs can cause nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, and also cardiovascular effects such as reduced blood pressure and shock. On the other hand, chronic exposure to iAs, may cause skin changes [hyperpigmentation, hyperkeratosis (thickening of the skin), and skin lesions], increased risk of several types of cancer (skin, bladder, lung, liver, and kidney), cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and neurological effects (numbness, and other symptoms of peripheral neuropathy).

Various health and environmental agencies have set limits on the allowable concentrations of inorganic arsenic in drinking water, food, and air to minimize exposure and associated health risks.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary inorganic arsenic intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the benchmark dose lower confidence limit based on a benchmark response (BMR) of 5% (BMDL₀₅) of 0.06 µg iAs/kg bw per day on skin cancer used also in EFSA's last scientific opinion (2024), and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary inorganic arsenic exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Inorganic arsenic (iAs) occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2022. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOD were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario and LOD for the Upper-bound scenario. Concentrations for mercury in human milk were taken from EFSA's opinion. A lot of the data measured and reported as total arsenic were converted to inorganic arsenic using different approaches, before calculating dietary exposure to iAs. Arsenic speciation results, i.e., amounts of iAs compounds, were available for rice and rice products. For other foods, the portion of iAs out of total arsenic was estimated to be 2 % in fish and 3.5% in crustaceans and molluscs,

100% in water and 70 % in other foods. The aggregated occurrence dataset contained 391 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contained 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 14.3 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Inorganic Arsenic summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.5.4

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Inorganic Arsenic
Substance Category	Contaminant
Value	0.06 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference	Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics for the whole population.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Inorganic Arsenic

key	Scenario		
	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0.004	0.008	0.013
Max	1.699	1.737	1.779
Mean	0.1	0.113	0.127
95% C.I.	(0.094 - 0.107)	(0.107 - 0.12)	(0.12 - 0.134)
SD	0.101	0.104	0.108
P25	0.042	0.052	0.063
Median	0.069	0.081	0.093
P75	0.121	0.137	0.154
P95	0.285	0.308	0.334
MoE (Mean)	0.597	0.529	0.473
MoE (P95)	0.21	0.195	0.179

* MoE:Margin of Exposure

Mean and 95th percentile exposure estimates at the MB scenario were calculated as 0.113 and 0.308 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day (Table 4.2). As inorganic arsenic is a genotoxic carcinogen a margin of exposure (MOE) approach was applied for the risk characterisation. The benchmark dose lower confidence limit based on a benchmark response (BMR) of 5% (BMDL₀₅) of 0.06 μg iAs/kg bw per day on skin cancer was selected as a Reference Point (RP) based on EFSA's last scientific opinion (2024).

The Reference Point (0.06 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw per day) for skin cancer is below the average dietary exposure estimates for iAs for the whole population. Therefore, the MOEs range between 0.5 for mean consumers and 0.2 at the 95th percentile exposure, respectively. These MOEs are relatively low and raise a health concern for skin cancer.

Taking into account other BMDL values from the literature for some of the studies on lung cancer, bladder cancer, ischemic heart disease and chronic kidney disease which are in the range 0.12–0.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw per day, these are close to the dietary exposure estimates, and therefore, there is a possible concern also for these endpoints.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	Median	P95	MoE (Mean)	MoE (P95)
FEMALE	0.016	1.287	0.106	(0.098 - 0.114)	0.094	0.078	0.266	0.568	0.226
MALE	0.008	1.737	0.121	(0.111 - 0.132)	0.113	0.084	0.329	0.495	0.182

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	Median	P95	MoE (Mean)	MoE (P95)
Ammochostos	0.027	1.075	0.125	(0.097 - 0.154)	0.113	0.082	0.378	0.480	0.159
Larnaka	0.018	0.876	0.107	(0.094 - 0.119)	0.089	0.077	0.293	0.563	0.204
Lefkosa	0.008	0.919	0.126	(0.112 - 0.14)	0.109	0.089	0.353	0.477	0.170
Lemesos	0.017	1.737	0.105	(0.094 - 0.115)	0.106	0.080	0.252	0.573	0.238
Pafos	0.016	0.961	0.101	(0.083 - 0.12)	0.099	0.074	0.257	0.593	0.233

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	Median	P95	MoE (Mean)	MoE (P95)
Adolescents	0.020	1.018	0.136	(0.121 - 0.151)	0.126	0.097	0.331	0.440	0.181
Adults	0.018	0.567	0.093	(0.085 - 0.102)	0.073	0.076	0.230	0.643	0.261
Elderly	0.008	1.287	0.085	(0.071 - 0.099)	0.113	0.060	0.219	0.706	0.274
Infants	0.033	0.985	0.227	(0.207 - 0.246)	0.164	0.198	0.520	0.265	0.115
Other children	0.040	0.876	0.215	(0.202 - 0.228)	0.114	0.200	0.422	0.279	0.142
Toddlers	0.068	1.737	0.304	(0.283 - 0.325)	0.178	0.261	0.610	0.197	0.098

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that infants, toddlers and other children had two- or three-times higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight.

The Reference Point ($0.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ per day) for skin cancer is within the range of the dietary exposure estimates for iAs for all population classes ($0.02\text{--}1.74 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$ per day) (Table 4.5). Therefore, the MOEs range between 0.2 and 0.7 for mean consumers and between 0.1 and 0.3 at the 95th percentile exposure, respectively. Despite the possible uncertainties, these low MOE values raise a health concern for skin cancer.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to iAs by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by iAs are consumed by all population classes.

Mean Inorganic Arsenic exposure (MB scenario)

Across Area and Population class

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total iAs exposure for the whole population is shown in Figure 4.7. Rice (11.9%) was the major contributor to the iAs intake, twice higher than the other food categories, cereal flakes (5.0%), poultry meat (4.5%), mineral water (4.3%), fish (3.4%) followed by other food categories. In all population classes, with the exception of infants and elderly, rice was the major contributor. In the case of infants because of their different consumption habits due to their age infant formula and cereal-based baby food were the main contributors to the iAs exposure (Figure 4.8). On the other hand, the consumption of fish in the elderly population contributed higher to iAs intake than rice.

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Inorganic Arsenic Total Exposure MB (whole population).

Figure 4.8: Contribution to the Inorganic Arsenic Total Exposure MB (infants).

Figure 4.9: Contribution to the Inorganic Arsenic Total Exposure MB (elderly).

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Inorganic Arsenic Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Infant formulae, liquid	4	Infants	17.10%
Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	4	Infants	16.73%
Rice and similar-	4	Toddlers	16.53%
Rice and similar-	4	Other children	13.61%
Rice and similar-	4	Adolescents	12.89%
Rice and similar-	4	ALL	11.89%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Elderly	11.46%
Rice and similar-	4	Adults	11.05%
Cereal flakes and similar	4	Other children	9.31%
Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	4	Infants	9.08%
Cereal flakes and similar	4	Adolescents	7.90%
Rice and similar-	4	Elderly	7.70%
Rice and similar-	4	Infants	7.20%
Follow-on formulae, liquid	4	Infants	6.89%
Octopuses	4	Adolescents	6.62%
Rusk	4	Elderly	6.44%
Shrimps and prawns	4	Adolescents	5.60%
Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	4	Toddlers	5.48%
Octopuses	4	Elderly	5.41%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Other children	5.26%
Other milks	4	Infants	5.14%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Natural mineral water	4	Elderly	5.10%
Bulgur	4	Other children	5.07%
Cereal flakes and similar	4	ALL	4.96%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Toddlers	4.75%
Natural mineral water	4	Adults	4.70%
Cereal flakes and similar	4	Toddlers	4.58%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	ALL	4.54%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Adults	4.53%
Bulgur	4	Toddlers	4.48%
Popped cereals	4	Other children	4.41%
Natural mineral water	4	ALL	4.30%
Celery leaves and similar-	4	Infants	4.25%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Adolescents	4.24%
Natural mineral water	4	Toddlers	4.07%
Natural mineral water	4	Other children	4.00%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Infants	3.92%
Squids	4	Adolescents	3.83%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Adolescents	3.79%
Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	4	Other children	3.77%
Natural mineral water	4	Adolescents	3.56%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	ALL	3.42%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Adults	3.28%
Wakame	4	Adults	3.28%
Cereal flakes and similar	4	Adults	3.27%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Bulgur	4	ALL	3.19%
Bulgur	4	Elderly	3.16%
Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	4	Toddlers	3.04%
Rusk	4	Adults	2.99%
Follow-on formulae, liquid	4	Toddlers	2.96%
Cucurbits with edible peel	4	Adults	2.92%
Biscuits, sweet, plain	4	Toddlers	2.90%
Octopuses	4	ALL	2.87%
Squids	4	Adults	2.86%
Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4	Elderly	2.84%
Cucurbits with edible peel	4	Elderly	2.83%
Octopuses	4	Other children	2.76%
Puffed cereals textured bread	4	Toddlers	2.72%
Cucurbits with edible peel	4	Other children	2.66%
Rusk	4	ALL	2.65%
Cucurbits with edible peel	4	ALL	2.60%
Bulgur	4	Adults	2.54%
Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	4	Adolescents	2.51%
Celery leaves and similar-	4	Elderly	2.47%
Bulgur	4	Adolescents	2.46%
Infant formulae, powder	4	Infants	2.41%
Squids	4	ALL	2.41%
Octopuses	4	Adults	2.30%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Rusk	4	Other children	2.26%
Crackers and breadsticks	4	Adults	2.26%
Crackers and breadsticks	4	Toddlers	2.26%
Flounders, halibuts, soles	4	Adults	2.24%
Biscuits, sweet, plain	4	Other children	2.21%
Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	4	Infants	2.16%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Other children	2.12%
Cucurbits with edible peel	4	Adolescents	2.08%
Popped cereals	4	Adolescents	2.07%
Pig fresh meat	4	Adults	2.01%
Celery leaves and similar-	4	Toddlers	2.00%
Rusk	4	Adolescents	1.97%
Squids	4	Other children	1.97%
Cereal flakes and similar	4	Elderly	1.94%
Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	4	ALL	1.92%
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes	4	Toddlers	1.91%
Shrimps and prawns	4	Adults	1.89%
Shrimps and prawns	4	ALL	1.89%
Cods, hakes, haddocks	4	Toddlers	1.89%
Flounders, halibuts, soles	4	Elderly	1.86%
Crackers and breadsticks	4	ALL	1.82%
Tap water	4	Elderly	1.80%
Cucurbits with edible peel	4	Toddlers	1.79%
Canned/jarred fish	4	Adults	1.78%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Puffed cereals textured bread	4	Other children	1.76%
Bottled drinking water	4	Adults	1.73%
Potatoes	4	Adults	1.69%
Wakame	4	ALL	1.69%
Onions	4	Elderly	1.68%
Crackers and breadsticks	4	Other children	1.68%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	Adults	1.68%
Onions	4	Toddlers	1.67%
Pig fresh meat	4	Adolescents	1.62%
Potatoes	4	Elderly	1.61%
Bottled drinking water	4	Infants	1.60%
Potatoes	4	ALL	1.58%
Pig fresh meat	4	ALL	1.58%
Cuttlefishes	4	Elderly	1.57%
Potatoes	4	Adolescents	1.57%
Tap water	4	Adults	1.53%
Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	4	Adults	1.51%
Onions	4	Adults	1.48%
Flounders, halibuts, soles	4	ALL	1.48%
Bottled drinking water	4	Toddlers	1.45%
Potatoes	4	Other children	1.44%
Tap water	4	Adolescents	1.44%
Onions	4	ALL	1.44%
Pig fresh meat	4	Elderly	1.42%
Bottled drinking water	4	ALL	1.42%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Biscuits, sweet, plain	4	ALL	1.42%
Tap water	4	ALL	1.41%
Onions	4	Other children	1.39%
Bananas and similar-	4	Toddlers	1.39%
Coffee beverages	4	Elderly	1.38%
Flat bread-based pastry	4	Elderly	1.38%
Canned/jarred fish	4	Elderly	1.37%
Canned/jarred fish	4	ALL	1.36%
Popped cereals	4	ALL	1.35%
Popped cereals	4	Toddlers	1.35%
Beans (dry) and similar-	4	Elderly	1.35%
Bottled drinking water	4	Adolescents	1.34%
Follow-on formulae, powder	4	Toddlers	1.33%
Potatoes	4	Toddlers	1.33%
Pasta, plain (not stuffed), uncooked	4	Other children	1.33%
Herrings, sardines, anchovies	4	Elderly	1.32%
Pasta, plain (not stuffed), uncooked	4	Toddlers	1.31%
Celery leaves and similar-	4	ALL	1.30%
Natural mineral water	4	Infants	1.30%
Squids	4	Elderly	1.29%
Biscuits, sweet, plain	4	Elderly	1.28%
Flat bread-based pastry	4	Adults	1.25%
Follow-on formulae, powder	4	Infants	1.24%
Salmons, trouts, smelts	4	ALL	1.23%
Biscuits, sweet, plain	4	Adolescents	1.21%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Potatoes	4	Infants	1.21%
Tap water	4	Other children	1.19%
Onions	4	Adolescents	1.18%
Spinaches and similar-	4	Elderly	1.16%
Bananas and similar-	4	Infants	1.16%
Pears and similar-	4	Infants	1.15%
Coffee beverages	4	Adults	1.14%
Celery leaves and similar-	4	Adults	1.13%
Canned/jarred fish	4	Other children	1.12%
Pancakes	4	Adolescents	1.10%
Pig fresh meat	4	Other children	1.09%
Biscuits, rusks and cookies for children	4	Infants	1.09%
Bulgur	4	Infants	1.09%
Lettuces and similar-	4	Adults	1.08%
Fish roe	4	Adolescents	1.07%
Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	4	Toddlers	1.07%
Tap water	4	Toddlers	1.07%
Cattle milk	4	Other children	1.06%
Canned/jarred fish	4	Adolescents	1.05%
Pasta, plain (not stuffed), uncooked	4	Adolescents	1.05%
Shrimps, common	4	Adults	1.05%
Shrimps and prawns	4	Other children	1.03%
Lettuces and similar-	4	Elderly	1.03%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Cods, hakes, haddocks	4	Elderly	1.01%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of iAs has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the aggregation of occurrence data	+/-
Use of the substitution method for non-detects	+/-
Use of weight coefficients for non-representativeness of the population	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as iAs concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an ICP-MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the

survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumptions taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation, conversion from total As to iAs) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean and 95th percentile exposure estimates at the MB scenario were calculated as 0.113 and 0.308 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). The Reference Point (0.06 µg/kg bw per day) for skin cancer is below the average dietary exposure estimates for iAs for the whole population. Therefore, the MOEs range between 0.5 for mean consumers and 0.2 at the 95th percentile exposure, respectively. These MOEs are relatively low and raise a health concern for skin cancer.

It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. Infants, toddlers and other children had two- or three-times higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight. Similarly to EFSA's findings the Reference Point (0.06 µg/kg bw per day) for skin cancer was within the range of the dietary exposure estimates for iAs for all population classes (0.02–1.74 µg/kg bw per day).

Rice (11.9%) was the major contributor to the iAs intake, twice higher than the other food categories, cereal flakes (5.0%), poultry meat (4.5%), mineral water (4.3%), fish (3.4%) followed by other food categories. In all population classes, with the exception of infants and elderly, rice was the major contributor. For infants, infant formula and cereal-based baby food were the main contributors to the iAs exposure, while the consumption of fish in the elderly population contributed higher to iAs intake than rice.

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices